

ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS FABRICATION

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Introduction

Acquisition and ownership costs of high performance aircraft are an accumulation of the following elements; development and production manufacturing costs, operation and maintenance costs and the effectiveness of the aircraft in performing its assigned tasks. Many studies in the use of composites in aircraft structures have shown that composites can significantly influence all these basic areas.

It has been shown that the performance of aircraft is improved through the application of composites by reducing structural weight and/or increasing aerodynamic efficiency, which in turn reduces size and/or increases payload and range. The inherent properties of composite material permit performance gains not possible with metals; higher aspect ratio, thinner surfaces, or aeroelastic tailoring for improved maneuverability or load relief. Designs which utilize the potential of composites in failsafe structures coupled with its outstanding fatigue resistance have improved overall reliability. Indications are that a composite aircraft would be easier to maintain due to its inherent environmental resistance, and ease of repair. Finally, studies indicate that with the correct design approach, continued material development, implementation of low cost tooling and fabrication techniques, the cost of manufacturing composite aircraft can be less than for conventional metal aircraft.

The ability to reduce cost has been particularly significant in manufacturing. Where one year ago each part was fabricated by

hand much like custom furniture, the process now is much more automated. An automated tape laying machine capable of 50 pounds of graphite/hour lays down large uncured plates of any thickness or fiber orientation. Even the bagging process is under study to eliminate the use of expendable materials. Materials with lower resin content are being studied to reduce excess resin bleed-out. This will save resin, reduce bleeder cost (material and labor) and make the bag process more reliable. Other studies have shown that attachment holes may be formed in the part during cure and eliminate the requirement to drill the part. These same studies indicate that these holes are better than drilled holes structurally.

Quality control costs are being reduced by the lowered need for inspection due to the improved reliability of mechanized layup plus the automation of the Q.C. methods themselves. There are fewer places for errors to occur and therefore less inspection requirements. Lastly, damaged composite parts can often be repaired to original quality easier and cheaper than metal parts. Composite parts can be built up to repair damage, whereas often the metal part has to be scrapped.

The most significant cost reduction impact of composites is that a fully committed system will be 20% to 25% smaller as measured by gross weight. Past experience has shown that system costs are closely related to gross weight. Therefore, not only is there the potential to reduce the cost of the airframe structure directly, but the smaller airplane for a given job means lower acquisition and ownership costs.

Fabrication

The two most significant factors controlling the cost of composite airframe structures are design and manufacturing. Producible designs that are specific for composites coupled closely with good manufacturing techniques will result in higher performance and lower cost airframe structures than is now obtainable with the traditional metals of construction. Key elements of the manufacturing plan are: 1) Design; 2) Raw Material; 3) Tooling; 4) Fabrication Methods. With the exception of the design function which is discussed elsewhere the three remaining elements will be discussed in detail.

Raw Material

Aerospace users of advanced composites do not, as a rule, make their own composite materials from the raw filament and matrix materials. The "raw material" of the aerospace user is already preassembled for him, by a supplier, from the proper

proportions of the proper constituents in the proper array, and partially processed to a stage where it can be conveniently shipped and handled. These embryo composite materials are referred to as prepregs (from filaments preimpregnated with matrix material.) Fabrication of high-quality composite structures is highly dependent on prepreg quality and uniformity in such particulars as uniformity of fiber spacing, number and distribution filaments, resin tack, etc. To insure standards of quality, both visual inspection and qualification strength testing are required.

Organic matrix prepregs are generally procured in a partially cured state, the so-called B-stage, to facilitate handling prior to final layup. The curing process is a time-temperature reaction in which the time to achieve complete cure is inversely related to the temperature; as a consequence, even at room temperature a spontaneous, irreversible curing reaction is taking place. The practical significance of this phenomenon is a finite shelf life during which the prepreg may be stored and still remain suitable for fabrication of composite parts. In actual practice, storage at subambient temperatures is used to extend shelf life, but this measure still does not completely stop the process.

Consequently, it is stipulated that organic matrix prepregs have shelf-life limitations which are a function of storage temperature. At bulk storage temperature below 0°F, a 3-month shelf life can be expected. It is generally assumed that 3 months at 0°F is a conservative shelf life; however, the manufacturer's recommendations should dictate the storage procedure.

Tooling

General

The majority of boron/epoxy and graphite/epoxy parts are currently fabricated on a combination layup and molding tool. Separate layup tools could have advantages when the cost can be justified by the number of parts to be produced during the length of the production run.

Common steel has been used as the predominant tooling material because of availability, low cost, and compatible coefficient of thermal expansion relative to that of advanced composites. Stainless steel is used extensively when severe radius forming is required. This is usually the case when fabricating substructural shapes.

Aluminum is frequently used as a tooling material when a slip sheet can be placed between composite and tool. Slip sheets

of thin-gage steel, Teflon-coated cloth (nonporous), and Teflon films have been used successfully. Aluminum is used with a slip sheet when the part (1) is flat, (2) has a constant radius, or (3) is simply contoured. When the contour is severe, the slip sheet material will not drape sufficiently and wrinkles are frequently encountered.

Varying densities of plastic tooling have been used in the fabrication of parts. The plastic tooling concept offers an inexpensive method, especially when a splash can be taken directly off a master model. Many programs still permit the direct substitution of advanced composites for metallic sheet in a production part or detail. These detail parts are usually available to serve as a master. Figure 1 shows a plastic mold used to fabricate a horizontal stabilizer. Reinforced fiberglass plastic tools are also acceptable concepts, but are more expensive. Methods of reducing composite tooling cost are under intensive investigation and include castable ceramic cement molds, nickel vapor form molds, and castable zinc alloy molds, and fiber reinforced composite tools.

Tools such as that shown in Figure 1 can be cast in a short time using a mechanical dispensing machine (mud machine). Plastic tooling materials are usually two-part systems whose parts must be stored separately, then mixed thoroughly, and dispensed air-free at a rapid rate.

Wash-out plaster molds have been used for some time in the ply-wrapping and filament-winding segment of the industry. Plaster molds are used when low production is anticipated and the parts are very complicated. After layup and cure, the mold material is broken or washed out with hot water.

The fiber reinforced tools are finding increasing interest for advanced composites as offering to the manufacture low cost, durable tools with controlled thermal expansion and therefore excellent control of tolerances. This is accomplished by using the same fiber in the tool as is going to be used for the part and designed for the known expansion characteristic of the material and the part.

Specific Tooling

Honeycomb. The sketches of Figure 2 show a tooling concept for a conventional honeycomb structure. In this sketch, loft data are converted into a set of facing (skin) molds. These molds are used to lay up and cure the skins. A splash can be taken from each skin for use as a Keller pattern for machining the honeycomb core. The core surfaces are parallel originally and

can be "set" to a flat plate with polyethylene glycol ether. In this manner, the core cannot move during machining operations. When the top side has been machined, the core should be removed from the base plate and "set" to the splash from the top mating skin. The opposite (bottom) side of the core can now be machined using the splash cast from the bottom skin as a pattern.

The core can be sectioned and machined either after machining the top side or after both sides have been contoured for installation of the hard points (rigid substructure spars, ribs, fittings, etc.) The advantage of bonding in the hard points after machining the top side is that the hard points will provide accurate reference points during machining of the bottom side. A "picture-frame" restraining fixture is required for this bonding operation. Intumescent adhesives are used to bond the core to edge members. Most of these bonding operations are done in an oven.

Skins and Closeouts. The last major operation is to bond the skins to the core as shown in the bottom sketch of Figure 2. In structures which have flanged closeouts of the spar type shown in this sketch, support is required under unsupported external flanges in the form of closely fitting filler blocks.

The sketches of Figure 3 show an alternate method of processing called "cocuring" which affects the tooling considerably. In this method, the skins are laminated and bonded to hard points and core simultaneously. It will be noted that the tooling is considerably simpler than for the previous method. Frequently, the core is machined by automatic numerical control based upon dimensions from the outer mold line surface less the thickness of the skins. Since honeycomb core cannot support itself, a plastic splash is made from the machined side. This splash holds the core in position as before while machining the outer side. At this point, the hard points are installed as in the previous method. The skin plies are laid up on Mylar templates in the same manner as in the previous method. Since an amount of resin will bleed out during cure, room must be provided in the tool for bleeder materials. In these sketches, the parts reflect two outer mold line skins which must have smooth aerodynamic surfaces. A thin caul sheet over the surface between the resin bleed system and vacuum bleeder cloth will produce an aerodynamically smooth surface.

In each of the methods, composite substructure shapes (hard points) are shown which sometimes become as expensive to produce as the remaining structure. Because of this expense, programs have been directed towards cheaper ways to fabricate such shapes. Typically, to fabricate a C-channel, large bars of steel would be obtained, machined, ground, and polished. Such tools would be

extremely heavy and would require several hours of machining time. As a result of these high costs, tooling development programs were initiated which resulted in C-channel molds that have been fabricated in 9 minutes using the brake forming method. In this case, the mold was fabricated from flat plates of 0.080-inch-thick stainless steel. The tool included draft angles of $92^{\circ} 30'$. Angles in excess of 90° are required to accommodate springback of the composite channel after cure. The angle of springback is dependent upon the ply orientation, type of composite, and laminate thickness. A springback allowance of 4° for graphite/epoxy (+45) channels was required in fabrication of a graphite stabilizer. Using a basic C-channel configuration, many other shapes can be produced by bonding various cut sections.

Views of typical tooling and fabrication sequences for honeycomb panel and sheet-stringer construction are shown in Figures 4 and 5, respectively.

For each of the advanced composites, there is a minimum bend radius. This type of data should be determined by the user for a specified system. Tools should be made with the most generous radii practical. Boron is especially sensitive to tight bend radii. Boron layups at 90° to the bend axis should not be less than 3-inch radius. The radius can be progressively reduced as the angle between the filaments and the bend axis approaches 0° . Producibility problems have not arisen using graphite or organic fiber in designs of normal aircraft radii.

Tooling Ground Rules

Basic tooling design rules for epoxy laminates may be summed as follows:

- a. Become familiar with materials and processes before designing a tool.
- b. Provide ample space for process control panels on face of tool.
- c. Perform leak checks on all metallic tools in which holes have been drilled.
- d. Perform leak checks on all nonmetallic tools used in conjunction with vacuum or autoclave pressure. Some plastic tools have leaked through the facing in thick sections. It is preferable that leak checks be conducted at pressures and temperatures anticipated during production.
- e. Don't build in producibility problems by using tight bend radii.

f. Don't use 2 pounds of steel when 1 pound will do the job; consider honeycomb tooling.

Fabrication Methods

The steps in the fabrication of composite parts are:

- Layup
- Laminate Cure*
- Joining*
- Machining

Hand Layup of Laminates

Composite laminates are assembled by proper placement of wide-goods or prepreg tapes ply by ply, following the required ply orientation and stacking order. When hand layup procedures are employed, it is common practice to preassemble plies on special plastic templates.

*Concurrent for cocured parts.

This procedure is performed in a clean area typical of those used in fiberglass and adhesive-bonding layup operations. The details are essentially as described in the following paragraphs.

Preparation of Individual Ply. Individual plies are prepared in the following sequence of steps:

- a. Allow tape raw material to warm to room temperature before opening sealed package to prevent moisture from condensing on tape. Place tape on a tape dispenser.
- b. Record spool or sheet and batch numbers of each ply of material at time it is used.
- c. Wipe exposed templates with clean cheesecloth moistened with acetone or methyl ethyl ketone, and air dry.
- d. Unroll sufficient prepreg for a strip of layup, and cut with sharp scissors, knife, or other suitable cutting tool.
- e. Place prepreg tape in area indicated on templates. Place adjacent tapes so that no gap in excess of 0.060 inch occurs for boron. Overlapped filaments are not permissible.

f. Work prepreg layup against template, using a wiping motion to insure intimate contact. Remove separator, strip.

g. Inspect each ply layup for filament, crossovers, gaps between tapes, and foreign matter contamination.

Laminate Layup. The laminate is laid up in the following sequence of steps:

a. Prepare layup tool as follows:

- Clean to remove all foreign material.
- Polish to develop a smooth surface.
- Wipe with suitable solvent, and air dry.
- Apply suitable release or parting agent.

b. Cover surface of tool with a Teflon-coated fabric (nonporous.)

c. Prepare a peel ply (only if surfaces of cured part are to be adhesively bonded.) Position one ply of set and heat-scoured nylon peel ply with 1/2-inch excess on all sides. Rub out with a squeegee to remove all air pockets and wrinkles. All splices shall be the butt type. Remove remaining separator film.

d. Tool-pin holes are provided to align the template precisely with respect to the tool.

e. Using roller or squeegee method, remove any air entrapped between plies.

f. Remove the Mylar templates.

g. Inspect each ply after template has been removed.

h. Repeat steps c. through g. until all required plies are laid up.

i. Use a balance ply of 104 glass scrim, impregnated with same resin, as last ply of a boron laminate.

Preparation for Cure. Cover the part with a release material perforated for resin bleed. The material should cover the entire part, but should not extend beyond its periphery. Boundary supports are required to prevent crowning by the bag and to restrict the amount of resin flow. Normally, these supports

are cork or metal sheet and are carefully sealed before use. Resin can flow through unsealed separations and mismatches between segments of the dam or between the dam and tool. Boundary supports for a top-bleed system should be within 0.060 inch of the part edge to prevent filament washing during resin flow stage. Figure 6 shows a typical boundary support system.

During the cure, each ply debulks (reduces from its original thickness) by voiding itself of entrapped air and resin. Therefore, each advanced composite material and part requires a different boundary support (dam.) Dams are fabricated by using one of the three following techniques:

- a. All cork - for use when the part is less than 100 plies and is to be trimmed.
- b. All metal - for use when the part is less than 100 plies and is fabricated net.
- c. Combination metal and cork - for use when the part is over 40 plies.

The dam height should always be less than the width to prevent lateral movement. The ratio of height to width should be no greater than 2:3. For laminates less than 100 plies, metal dams should be the same height as the desired cured laminate thickness, while cork dams should be 10:7 greater than this thickness to allow for cork debulking.

For laminates over 100 plies and using a combination cork and metal dam material, the metal portion of the dam should be of the same height as three-fourths of the desired cured laminate thickness, while the remainder of the dam should be Coroprene of a height equal to the remaining one-fourth of the laminate thickness times a factor of 10:7. Aluminum pressure-sensitive tape may be placed under the dam to act as a seal to prevent excess resin loss.

One ply of dry 120 glass fabric is applied for each five plies of boron prepreg. The 120 glass should be the same size as the part and should not extend beyond the periphery of the part. This 1-to-5 relationship between dry 120 glass and the prepreg provides a controlled bleed of the resin. This same control can be accomplished with a combination of 116 glass and felt. The relationship is shown in the following listing:

<u>Plies of Boron/Epoxy</u>	<u>Plies of 116 Glass</u>	<u>Thickness of Felt (in.)</u>
10	2	0
15	4	0
20	2	1/16
30	2	1/8
40	2	3/16
50	2	1/4
60	2	5/16
70	2	3/8
80	2	7/16
90	2	1/2
100	2	9/16

For laminates in excess of 100 plies, the felt should be increased 1/16 inch for each 10 additional plies of prepreg.

A layer of plastic film such as Teflon should be placed over the entire layup so that the edges extend well beyond the periphery of the part. For the escape of air from the controlled/flow bleed system described previously, pierce holes in the plastic film with a pointed instrument 0.060 inch in diameter. The holes should be on approximately 2-inch centers. Cover the entire layup with two plies of 181 glass fabric for vacuum bag venting.

The entire layup should be held securely against the tool during all subsequent handling until the part is in the autoclave for cure. The controlled-flow bleeder system is shown in Figure 7.

In the laminate bleed system shown, a portion of the resin flow occurs through the controlled gap between the laminate edge and the dam or boundary supports. The volume of resin to be bled from the composite prepreg is calculated and equated to the gap volume. A simple trial-and-error solution is employed to determine the gap dimension. Additional tailoring of the gap dimension may be accomplished if the edge bleeding is limited to laminate lateral edges. Laminates up to 10 by 65 inches have been fabricated with this controlled-flow bleed system at the desired ply thickness for the cured composite. It is necessary that the boundary supports be principally metal and that their position be properly maintained, since the gap void must be maintained under the cure temperature and pressure conditions preceding resin flow. Approximately 1/16-inch-thick aluminum caul plates, sized to the laminate layup dimensions, may be utilized as a precaution against cured laminate bag surface irregularities and excessive resin loss from the top composite plies into the vacuum bag vent cloth. Each organization should conduct a controlled resin-flow edge-bleed process investigation for the raw material type, laminate thickness, and related cure cycle for its own application.

Machine Layup of Laminates

The objectives of machine layup are to eliminate the human error, improve the laminate quality (low void content), and to speed up the fabrication process (lower cost.) Some of the problems encountered with developing tape layup machines have been tape tack, tape alignment, indexing of tape orientation through numerical control, and layup of curved surfaces. A major hindrance in the use of these machines in substructure fabrication has been the inability to wrap tapered components while maintaining a constant laminate orientation.

Tape Layup Machines. Tape-laying machines, as they exist today, range from hand-operated dispensing heads on a track, to fully automated machines. The simplest of these is shown in Figure 8. As shown in this example, a single operator manually operates the laydown head and manually cuts the tape. There are many variations that can be applied to this basic concept, such as a cutting device on the head, a table base that rotates for different tape orientations, a continuous belt system for indexing the Mylar template, and others that can be adapted to suit a particular application. A typical first-generation, automated, three-axis tape-laying machine was constructed to have a laying area of 72 by 80 inches, a three-axis control system, a vertical head motion of 10 inches (by pneumatic actuator), a maximum tape-lay of 2 pounds of 4.0 -mil boron or 2.5 pounds of 5.6 -mil boron per hour, and an average production rate of 1-1/8 pound per hour. A closeup view of the tape-dispensing head is shown in Figure 9. As can be seen, the backing paper on the boron tape has edge perforations so that the tape can be fed in a similar manner to motion picture film.

A second-generation machine which represents the current state of automated technology is a five-axis machine, which is shown in Figure 10. This machine has the following features:

Laying Area - 72 x 360 inches

Manual, semiautomatic, and automatic five-axis control system:

X-Axis - Longitudinal (720 in./min maximum)

Y-Axis - Transverse (720 in./min maximum)

C-Axis - Head rotation ($\pm 180^\circ$)

D-Axis - Shear rotation ($\pm 60^\circ$)

P-Axis - Tape transport (40 in./min)

Vertical head motion - 7 inches (pneumatic actuator)

Air bearing worktable which will support 125 lb/ft² tool loads

Shear which will operate at all tape-laying speeds

Maximum tape-lay - 36 pounds per hour of 4.0 -mil boron or 45 pounds per hour of 5.6 mil boron

Average production rate - 13 pounds per hour of 4.0 -mil boron or 16 pounds per hour of 5.6 -mil boron.

Those utilizing machine layup techniques now find the ply template previously discussed may be eliminated, and the machine can be programmed to place the tape in the desired orientation for the required number of plies automatically. Both the preparation and the cure of a machine-laidup composite are the same as described for a hand-laidup composite.

Pultrusion. Pultrusion is a new technique to fabricate structural elements such as stringers. Basically, advanced composite fibers are drawn through a heated ceramic die which forms and cures the particular cross-sectional shape selected. It offers significant cost reduction in subcomponent fabrication and is under intensive development.

After the composite laminate detail has been laid up, either by hand or by machine, and the cure preparations completed, the detail is ready for cure. Several cure process methods can be adapted to provide the required pressure, time, and temperature schedule. This subsection includes a typical cure schedule for processing epoxy composites by the methods of vacuum bag, autoclave, blanket press, platen press, and compression molding, the most widely used of which is the vacuum-bagged layup in an autoclave.

Epoxy composite fabricators have observed that an exothermic reaction occurs during cure, which can result in severe cure temperature overruns. The exotherm heat generated during the cure of thin laminates is usually transmitted into the tooling by conduction. For thick-section laminates, however, when using a simple cure cycle, the cure reaction heat cannot be dissipated rapidly enough and the epoxy resin cure reaction presents a problem which results in significantly reduced laminate mechanical properties or even charred matrix resin. Control of the exotherm temperature overrun has been achieved by a step cure. Each organization should conduct its own investigation based on part thickness, cure process, method, and matrix type for its particular requirements.

Standard Autoclave Cure for Thin Laminates. The standard autoclave cure cycle can be applied to prepreg layups of 40 plies or less. The laminate layup is installed in the autoclave while under full vacuum, and the autoclave pressure is then raised to 20 to 30 psig. The bagged layup vacuum line is next vented to atmospheric pressure, and the pressure is raised to full cure pressure, followed by autoclave heat-up to cure temperature. A typical cure is as follows. The part is heated directly to 350° (+10°F), using a temperature climb rate of 8° (+2°F) per minute. The temperature is held at 350°F for 120 (+30, -10) minutes, and pressure is maintained at 85 (+) psi. After the proper time at temperature, the part is cooled to less than 150°F before removing the pressure. There should be less than 50°F between the hottest and coldest thermocouple reading on the part during cool-down. Warping is a serious problem resulting from extreme hot and cold spots during cool-down.

Standard Autoclave Cure for Thin-Skinned Cocured Composite Structures. The cure schedule for honeycomb structures with thin facing is the same as the standard cure, except for the pressure. Variables of core density, cell size, skin thickness and orientation, etc affect the pressure to be used. Optimum pressure should be the maximum tolerable without inducing permanent set in the core or excessive impression of the cell edges showing through the laminate. A typical sandwich cure pressure is between 35 to 50 psi.

Extended Autoclave Cure for Thick Laminates. An extended or thick laminate autoclave cure cycle should be applied to any prepreg layup in excess of 40 plies. Typical exotherm cure cycles include dwell steps at temperatures below the final cure temperature. These dwell steps serve to control the exotherm reaction rate by extending the reaction over a longer time period to dissipate the generated heat and thereby control the temperature within acceptable limits.

The vacuum bag autoclave cure cycles may be utilized for composite laminate curing with blanket pressure equipment, except that vacuum bagging operations may be accomplished more economically with the blanket press equipment vacuum system. Other considerations affecting selection of the blanket press method include detail part geometry and cure cycle temperature control.

Platen Press Cure. If matched metal tooling is not used, the edges of the laminate parallel to the filament orientation must be restricted to prevent filament washout. This can be accomplished by wrapping the layup in an envelope of several wraps of high-temperature release-treated separator paper or fabric. The edges

of the envelope-wrapped layup should include provisions for entrapped-air escape. Laminated parts designed for fabrication by matched metal molding require cure techniques similar to heated platen press cures. The cure schedule details should be established, however, on the basis of the part geometry, thickness, matrix type, and mold tools for the particular requirements of each organization.

It should be noted that exotherm heat dissipation by conduction into the heat sink of the press platens and/or mold will tend to minimize thick-section exotherm problems.

Process Controls. Typical of advisable in-process cure controls are vacuum bag leakage checks, time-oriented cure pressure records, and time-oriented cure temperature records for both the part and the heat source. Nondestructive testing of the laminate should be conducted to determine filament gaps, filament cross-overs, wrinkles and warpage, specific gravity, Barcol hardness, and the location and extent of delamination or void areas. Destructive testing, in addition to the determination of mechanical properties of laminate specimens fabricated and processed concurrently with the detail parts, can be extended to include tests of the finished parts in accordance with a sampling schedule. Naturally, the scope and degree of the quality controls applied to a specific detail part depend upon the desired level of reliability with suitable detail part complexity and cost trade-off considerations.

Joining

Two methods of attachment are discussed: adhesive bonding and mechanical fastening. The bonding technique is emphasized because of its importance in saving structural weight in composite components.

Adhesive Bonding. There are two forms of composite bonding: cocuring and secondary bonding. Investigations have shown that cocuring requires fewer tools and, hence, less labor hours; however, when cocuring on honeycomb core some properties are degraded because of lower than normal laminating pressure. "Embossing" (the imprint of honeycomb cells through the cocured facings) also degrades the skin properties under compressive loading. The extent of property loss as a result of cocuring honeycomb panels is dependent upon cell size, skin thickness (number of plies), and ply orientation. The cocuring process is now under investigation to reduce the cost of advanced composite components.

Basically, the overall bonding technique is a three-step process: selection of adhesive, surface preparation, and bond cycle. These steps will be discussed in succeeding paragraphs.

1. Adhesive Selection. One of the most important steps in bonding is to choose the correct adhesive system. Guidelines for choosing an adhesive are as follows:

a. It must meet the strength requirements of a particular design in the stated environment.

b. It must be compatible with the laminate resin system.

c. It must have adequate tack for the particular number of bond cycles required.

d. It must have a low-enough modulus relative to the adherends to permit a fairly uniform stress distribution without excessive edge concentration.

2. Surface Preparation. Perhaps the most important step in bonding concerns proper surface preparation. The following sections describe surface preparation methods for the various types of materials used in component fabrication. Aluminum sheet will not be discussed since there is a vast data bank on this material.

a. Honeycomb Core. Aluminum and fiberglass cores are being used in sandwich structures which are both bonded and cocured. The method of cleaning cores depends upon the condition of the core after previous processing. In the case where core has been machined in the before-expansion state or held in position by double-backed tape, the core is cleaned by the standard vapor degreaser method. When core is "set" by polyethylene glycol ether (polyglycol), the core (after machining) should be washed thoroughly with hot water (over 160°F), alkaline cleaned, rinsed with deionized water, and quickly dried. Aluminum core should be carefully examined for stain or possible corrosion after the cleaning operation.

b. Titanium. Research efforts to develop a surface preparation method for titanium have resulted in several inconsistent methods. The one method that has proved to be the most consistent is the vapor-honing method. This technique has worked consistently and has produced cohesive failure within the adhesive.

Other techniques for preparing adhesive or resin-bonded joints have been used by various organizations involved in utilization of titanium structures. A review of the literature on titanium bonding reveals that bond strengths may be highly variable

and, under some circumstances, quite unpredictable. The experience of previous investigators is not surprising in light of current knowledge that bond strength is highly sensitive to the chemical condition of the metal surface.

A second method is the immersion phosphate fluoride treatment. This procedure has produced the best results thus far. Scanning electron micro-photographs of prepared surfaces have revealed that slight changes in processing and solution concentration can have impact on the bondability of the metal. Also, studies show that surface activity continues during the first 24 hours after the drying operation, and that the best results are obtained on surfaces primed and bonded immediately after the surface preparation.

c. Steel. Fortunately, steels can be more readily prepared for bonding than titanium. One method which has been generally accepted by the industry is as follows:

- (1) Remove oil and grease by MEK wipe or vapor degrease methods.
- (2) Grit blast with 180 grit aluminum oxide, using 60 to 90 psi air pressure.
- (3) Wipe with a clean cloth dampened with MEK.
- (4) Alkaline-clean in accordance with industry standards.
- (5) Rinse with tap water.
- (6) Immerse in 20 to 55 percent HNO_3 at temperature of 65°F minimum for 90 (+30) minutes.
- (7) Rinse in deionized water, and dry.

d. Composites. Two methods have proved successful in composite surface preparation. The first is the peel ply method, where heat-sealed and scoured nylon peel-ply material is applied to the B-stage laminate in the area to be subsequently bonded. This material does not wrinkle easily and produces a suitable surface. The ultrasonic NDT methods are applicable with the peel ply intact. After NDT, the peel ply can be removed, providing a surface ready for bonding. The second method is grit blasting with a fine aluminum oxide. Both methods have produced approximately the same shear ultimate strength of bond using Sheel 951 adhesive and graphite/epoxy laminates.

3. Bond Cycle. To achieve proper bonds in a structure, correct heat-up rates for the adhesive must be maintained. This is usually ascertained through subcomponent tests conducted during the design stage.

a. Mechanical Fastening. Mechanical fastening is normally used to attach advanced composite structures when high peel stresses are present, when fail-safe criteria are required, or when periodic disassembly of the joint is mandatory. For example, internal fuel pressure gives rise to unacceptable peel (or flatwise tension) stresses within bonded joints in a wing integral fuel tank; hence, mechanical attachment is required. Use of mechanical fasteners, however, gives rise to serious stress concentrations. Two ways to alleviate these concentrations involve replacing 0° laminae adjacent to the holes with (1) metallic interleaf strips and (2) softening strips of fiberglass or $\pm 45^\circ$ Gr/Ep.

Bucked rivets are not recommended for advanced composite joints, but squeezed or pull rivets have been used. When bolts are employed, the choice between standard heads (exterior or counterbored) or countersunk heads is largely a question of design constraints and the reduced net section produced. When aluminum fasteners are used with graphite/epoxy, it is suggested the fasteners have a protective treatment to prevent corrosion problems.

b. Machining Epoxy Laminates. Boron/epoxy composites present a challenge in the area of machining. The epoxy matrix is relatively easy to machine, but its comparative weakness in some cases does not provide adequate support to the boron filaments to prevent fiber breakout. The boron filament itself presents other difficulties because its hardness approaches 9.5 on the Mohs scale. Conventional hard cutting materials, such as tungsten carbide, aluminum oxide, silicon carbide, and tool steel, are softer than boron. While diamond, with a hardness of 10 on the Mohs scale, has been shown to be effective for machining boron/epoxy composites, considerable problems have been experienced when composite and interleaved metallic laminae must be machined together. For certain edge attachment designs, for example, drills have been changed at each interface between metal and composite. When thin foil metallic interleaves are used, this method is obviously impractical and a compromise machining system is necessary.

A number of less conventional machining approaches have been investigated, including laser cutting, electromagnetic machining, and various combinations of tools with ultrasonic energy. Problems have included resin burning and poor tolerance control. In addition to diamond-faced tools, some manufacturers have used a variety of drills for metallic composite combinations. High-speed steel drills, piloted-core cobalt twist drills, and carbide space drills have been tried, frequently followed by a diamond-surfaced reamer for final sizing and finish.

In the case of graphite and other organic fibers, standard steel twist drills, counter-sinks, and routers have been used extensively and have not shown the need for specialized techniques or equipment. However, the drilling of certain of the organic fibers may produce excessive tool wear because of their high toughness. Delamination can occur when drilling through composite. To prevent push-out when the drill breaks through the back side, masking tape should be placed over the area and the hole drilled slowly.

In summary it is obvious that numerous options for fabrication exist today and many more advanced concepts are under development.

The foregoing discussion has discussed in considerable detail the various options and specifics of advanced composites fabrication; however, a better insight may be obtained by taking a look at the manufacturing sequence relative to component fabrication.

Typical Component Manufacture

The following discussion will look at the pertinent steps in the fabrication procedure of different types of advanced composite aircraft structural configurations. For the sake of brevity, a and b will be discussed. These configurations may be categorized as:

- a. Full-depth honeycomb sandwich structure
- b. Spar/rib built-up structure
- c. Selective reinforcement structure
- d. Molded structure
- e. Tape/filament-wound structure

Full-Depth Honeycomb Sandwich Structure

The majority of advanced composite structures to date have been full-depth honeycomb sandwich components because of simplicity in construction coupled with utilization of the properties of composites in an optimum manner. To demonstrate the fabrication process for this type of configuration, the horizontal stabilizer of the Northrop F-5 aircraft was selected for discussion.

The F-5 graphite/epoxy horizontal stabilizer is an all-movable surface with an approximate platform area of 25 square feet. Several

manufacturing methods were developed through subelement component tests prior to the fabrication of the full-scale horizontal component. A detail view prior to assembly bonding of the component is shown in Figure 11. The procedures used to fabricate the article can be summarized as follows:

a. The spar and closeout rib subsections were laid up as wet graphite in the flat plane, formed as C sections in matched tools (as shown in Figure 12), and press cured. The final spar configuration was fabricated by bonding the C-channels back-to-back.

b. Graphite plies for the upper and lower skins were cut to Mylar templates and stacked for ready assembly. The plies were laid up on the respective aluminum tools and cured to form the skin configuration. The skins were then used as masters from which splashes were taken to machine the core.

c. The core was "set" with polyglycol on a flat plate while contouring on one side using one plastic splash as a pattern. The core was then removed from the flat plate, turned over, and reset for completion of the core machining using the second plastic splash.

d. The inboard and outboard ribs were fabricated by first taking epoxy splashes in the rib areas of both the upper and lower skins; then, after establishing airfoil chord planes, bonding the two splash halves together to form male tools. A female splash was then taken and used to lay up and cure the two ribs.

e. The substructural shapes (spar and closeout) were trimmed to drawing dimensions and prefitted to a production root end as shown in Figure 13.

f. The details were then assembled for the prefit operations. Obvious misfits were corrected with the verification film method utilized for a precise study of detail fit conditions.

g. All details were cleaned and the metallic details were primed prior to component assembly bonding.

h. The details were reassembled with structural adhesive placed at the faying surfaces. The part assembly was then bagged for cure in an autoclave under heat and pressure. A typical cure schedule of this operation has been shown in the previous discussion.

i. The completed horizontal stabilizer assembly is shown in Figure 14.

Selectively Reinforced Structure

With this technique, advanced composites are bonded locally to selected areas of conventional metal structure to augment its strength, stiffness, and/or fatigue characteristics. The components chosen to illustrate this configuration are the B-1 boron/epoxy to steel/titanium fuselage longerons, as shown in Figure 15.

The previous examples of manufacturing methods have utilized thin laminate parts. This component, however, requires thick laminates (i.e., 1.8 inches) to meet the design requirements. Two major problems were experienced with this type of part, viz: (1) exotherm and (2) difference in thermal coefficient of expansion combined with asymmetrical cross sections, resulting in warpage. The basic part in Figure 15 consists of a metallic strap (either titanium or steel) and a thick (bonded and cocured) boron/epoxy laminate.

The following outline indicates the procedures leading to the final assembly:

a. The metallic strap was fabricated as a separate detail; the bonding surface prepared as described in an earlier section and primed.

b. Figure 16 is the laminating and bonding tool used to fabricate the thick laminate. The strap was placed within the cavity of the dam. Structural adhesive was applied over the fay surface of the strap.

c. Spanwise unidirectional plies were cut to scaled dimensions and were prepared for layup. Since the part width was 4 inches (1 inch wider than the prepreg tape available), another section of 3-inch tape was slit into 1-inch strips to lay parallel with the 3-inch tape to supply the required prepreg width. Attempts were made to lay up the part without the aid of templates; however, it was found that the material would not conform and difficulty was encountered maintaining lengths in relationship to the tool. Tests revealed that when splicing plies, the splices should be a minimum of 0.75 inch from those in adjacent plies. The plies were tapered approximately one-quarter inch in the joint area, as shown in Figure 17. Sawtooth 90° plies were placed in the laminate to ameliorate the thermal warpage stresses.

d. The part was fabricated net; therefore, no cork was used under the dam sections. Pressure sensitive aluminum tape (two plies) was placed under the dam to seal against resin bleed.

e. Monitoring of temperatures in the part was required to insure that the laminate temperature was below 150°F prior to removing the autoclave pressure.

f. A completed boron/epoxy to metal longeron is shown in Figure 18.

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

Mold for Hat Section Pre-cured Reinforcement

Mold for Skin

Hat Section Stiffener Mold

Bonding Tool for Attaching Hat Section Stiffeners to Skin

FIGURE 5

FIGURE 6

FIGURE 7

FIGURE 8

FIGURE 9

FIGURE 10

FIGURE 11

FIGURE 12

FIGURE 13

FIGURE 14

FIGURE 15

FIGURE 16